

On the structural limitations and resulting opportunities of algorithmic gender and country predictions for diversity assessment in research

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Algorithmic tools like NamSor, which infer gender, country of origin, and ethnicity from author names, are increasingly used to support diversity monitoring in research policy. However, such classification tools may embed biases or produce unreliable results that could undermine the equity goals they aim to serve. This study undertakes a three-part assessment of NamSor's utility and limitations. First, we independently evaluate NamSor's performance using the WiBeF 2019 dataset—approximately 7,000 self-declared survey responses from Germany-based researchers—focusing on gender and country of origin classifications. Second, we show two policy applications where NamSor performs reliably: gender equality strategy evaluation and researcher mobility monitoring. Third, we pursue ongoing work examining the trade-offs between sample restriction and accuracy gains and conduct a systematic review of publications employing NamSor to identify potentially misleading results. Our findings contribute to a more critical and prudent attitude towards onomastic tools for diversity assessment in research.

1. Introduction

Creating a fair, high-quality, and socially responsible research ecosystem requires addressing researcher diversity. Hence, research policy increasingly promotes intersectional approaches, incorporating gender and ethnicity equality plans, integrating diversity into research content, and monitoring participation and content.

Algorithmic tools like NamSor, an online onomastic tool that infers gender, country of origin, and ethnicity from author names in bibliometric databases, can support this work (NamSor, 2026; Sebo, 2023).

It can either spare time and resources or even unveil socio-demographic patterns whose available data won't manage to show. For example, NamSor could be especially beneficial in bibliometric analyses for identifying country of origin or ethnicity when such data is absent, facilitating the examination of cross-cultural disparities in research, publication inequities, or citation patterns of scientific articles associated with the origins of researchers, reviewers, or editors, as well as for any broader study incorporating origin as a variable of interest. Such studies typically necessitate extensive datasets, and self-identification of country of origin or ethnicity is frequently unfeasible.

As a matter of fact, NamSor has been employed in over 600 scientific publications.

As largely advertised on its official website to support a declared higher level of precision compared to other solutions, NamSor has been positively evaluated by a bunch of institutions and companies for diverse purposes, such as Science-Metrix for Elsevier, the EU's SheFigures gender statistics, Harvard and the Univ. of Chicago, Uber, and Research Square (NamSor, 2026).

NamSor employs a specialized NLP engine and relies on comprehensive databases that correlate names (7+ billion names, 22 alphabets) with cultural, ethnic, and linguistic

backgrounds. However, in general, performance metrics are contingent on data curation and selection and fundamental assumptions guiding training and validation processes. Moreover, as widely shown in literature, behind an assumed belief of impartiality, classification ML/AI tools can often embed or even amplify systemic discrimination if their training relies on biased datasets or their modelling approach exploits simplistic empirical observations. Additionally, regarding this specific case, these tools might even reinforce those inequalities they aim to measure and become performative.

Sebo (2023) demonstrated that the likelihood of NamSor's misclassification is elevated concerning country of origin or ethnicity; nonetheless, it diminishes, similar to continent of origin, when employing the modified variable and/or the subsample with an accuracy of at least 50%. However, narrowing a sample (because of an assessment tool's poor performances otherwise) might likely invalidate those sample features that were essential to a given study. In other words, the prerequisite of a study might fall short as the subsample doesn't describe any longer what the sample did.

This work consists of three main steps. Firstly, in light of the above, we assess NamSor performance independently on a whole sample. To this end, the WiBeF 2019 dataset (Fabian et al., 2025), i.e., the collection of about 7000 anonymous, survey-self-declared responses from Germany-based researchers, sounds like a good candidate. The WiBeF sample is representative of the German research landscape at several and diverse levels; a subsample of it most likely cannot keep the same properties (unless an exact combination of isomorphic alterations) and thus doesn't represent Germany any longer. We mainly focus on gender and country of origin dimensions.

Secondly, we propose two policy exercises that meet NamSor utility alongside outcome reliability; in light of the performance assessment above, we carry out two policy applications, namely, gender equality strategies evaluation and mobility monitoring, taking advantage of those contingencies where the NamSor outcome is reliable.

Our third and in-progress step is twofold. Firstly, we aim at assessing the sample features' loss alongside the actual gain in performances. Fine-tuning of NamSor variables (e.g., the second-guessed country and country accuracy) will shrink the sample alongside increasing the subsample's overall accuracy.

Secondly, we aim to qualify the research production that involves NamSor usage (i.e., more than 600 papers). Specifically, in light of the warnings that emerged from our performance assessment, those gray papers' declared outcomes might be misleading, especially if policy implications are involved. We propose to conduct a systematic literature review (scientific mapping?) in order to identify those scientific areas where NamSor has been employed. In addition, through text analysis on the abstracts, we aim at collecting all those applications whose results are directly related to NamSor usage and assess the extent of potential misleading/incorrect results (e.g., policy implications).

2. Performance Validation of NamSor

To evaluate the accuracy of NamSor in identifying researchers' countries of origin and gender, we used data from the WiBeF 2019 survey. This dataset includes 6,722 researchers working in Germany, of whom 5,757 (approximately 86%) are German nationals and 965 are from other countries (Fabian et al., 2025).

2.1 Country of Origin

The results reveal substantial limitations in NamSor's ability to accurately infer countries of origin from names. Among the 5,757 German researchers, 2,682 were misclassified, corresponding to a misclassification rate of 46.6% and an accuracy rate of only 53.4%. Many German names were incorrectly attributed to neighboring or "culturally related" countries such as Austria, Switzerland, Denmark, Sweden, the Netherlands, France, Israel, Belgium, and Greece.

NamSor systematically misclassified all the individuals from all the Americas. Latin American countries—including Brazil, Mexico, Colombia, Chile, Argentina, Venezuela, and Ecuador—originate from Spain, Portugal, or Italy (totally 37). Researchers from Canada and the United States were also labeled as European (37 as well). A total of 74 such misclassifications were documented. These results indicate persistent algorithmic biases linked to colonial legacies, wherein names from formerly colonized regions are associated with their European colonizer countries.

NamSor's performance for Israel-associated classifications reveals an additional source of bias. The tool identified 80 researchers as being from Israel, yet only 2 individuals in the dataset were actually Israeli nationals. Strikingly, 79 of the 80 identified cases were incorrect, with 74 of those individuals being German. This pattern reflects NamSor's inability to account for sensitive nuances of ethnic and cultural diversity, leading to erroneous groupings. The disproportional misidentification of German names as Israeli is particularly illustrative of these limitations.

2.2 Gender Identification

In contrast to its performance on country of origin, NamSor showed a high overall accuracy in gender prediction (97%). However, this aggregate figure conceals important disparities. The system exhibited poor calibration for individuals with Asian names, where predictions were noticeably less reliable. Furthermore, the tool's design inherently excludes researchers who do not identify within the male–female binary, thereby reinforcing restrictive gender classifications and overlooking non-binary identities. This limitation highlights the need for more inclusive algorithmic frameworks that account for the diversity of gender expressions in contemporary research populations.

3. Policy Applications of NamSor

Despite the methodological limitations highlighted above, NamSor can still offer valuable insights when applied critically and under certain controlled conditions. Since the WiBeF dataset acts as a representative German sample, we identify two potential policy-oriented case studies within the German science system where the tool's accuracy is demonstrated to be high for some specific measures. In these cases, the tool's predictions can inform discussions on research policy and demographic/mobility dynamics within academia.

3.1 Case Study 1: Gender Equality Monitoring in Research

Motivation:

Since the early 2000s, Germany's Federal Ministry of Education and Research (BMBF) has pursued a sustained policy agenda aimed at reducing gender disparities in education and research. Over the past decade, these efforts have intensified through national action plans and funding programs such as MINT for STEM, WISER, and various STEM role model initiatives that promote women's participation in scientific careers.

Analytical framework:

NamSor's gender inference capabilities could be used to approximate gender distributions among German authors of scientific publications between 2015 and 2023, as indexed in Scopus. By aggregating its gender predictions, one could assess the *overall trends* in female authorship over this period, offering a broad indicator of the progress achieved under BMBF's equality policies.

Findings:

As shown in Fig. 1, at the aggregate level, the data suggest that female authorship reached approximately 30% in 2023, indicating measurable progress toward gender parity. However, a closer examination of authorship roles—particularly first and last author positions, which typically denote intellectual leadership and seniority—reveals that gender inequalities persist more strongly in influential positions. This implies that while gender balance may appear improved in terms of overall participation, substantive equality in research leadership remains a longer-term challenge. In Fig. 2 is reported the same plot for WiBeF data, showing high agreement and thus consistency in treating it as a sample on the whole German author landscape.

Figure 1: German Female Authorships over the timeframe 2015-2023.

Figure 2: WiBef Female Authorships over the timeframe 2015-2023 (as a validation exercise).

3.2 Case Study 2: Scientific Mobility Between China and Germany

Motivation:

Monitoring international researcher mobility remains a policy priority in Germany, exemplified by the annual “Wissenschaft Weltoffen” report jointly published by the German Academic Exchange Service (DAAD) and the German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW). Understanding such mobility trends contributes to national strategies for international cooperation and talent circulation.

Analytical framework:

Using NamSor’s *country of origin* predictions, we can approximate cross-national researcher mobility—illustrated in Fig. 3 by flows between China (CHN) and Germany (DEU). Mobility events are based on changes in affiliations between 1997 and 2024.

Findings:

Three main trends emerge from this case study:

1. German names remain marginal within the bilateral mobility flow, indicating limited outbound movement relative to broader international exchanges.
2. Names from other cultural and linguistic contexts show a steady increase, reflecting the growing diversity of global research collaboration.
3. Chinese names dominate the exchange pattern, suggesting that Chinese nationals increasingly represent the primary cohort of mobile researchers between China and Germany.

Figure 3: Mobility events are based on changes in affiliations between 1997 and 2024.

4. Conclusions and Work in Progress

4.1 Conclusions

The evaluation of NamSor’s performance demonstrates that, while the tool holds substantial potential for large-scale analysis of demographic patterns in science, it also presents significant methodological and ethical challenges. Within the WiBeF 2019 dataset, NamSor’s predictions were primarily tested on a population consisting of 86% German researchers, which constrains the generalizability of the findings. The accuracy for *country of origin* classification for Germans was only 53.4%. Evident biases linked to colonial naming legacies emerge. These findings underscore that, without explicit recognition of its structural and epistemic limitations, NamSor risks reproducing or amplifying inequalities—precisely the patterns it might otherwise help to reveal.

Yet, within carefully defined and critically interpreted boundaries, NamSor can still offer policy-relevant insights. Two key areas of opportunity stand out:

1. Gender prediction, where—despite binarism limitations—the tool can help assess the aggregate impact of gender equality initiatives in research and higher education.

2. Country of origin inference can inform mobility studies and help monitor trends in international researcher circulation.

4.2 Work in Progress

1. Integration of NamSor Confidence/Accuracy Measures, Second Country of Origin, and Sample Narrowing:

The current validation was performed on the entire WiBeF sample, deliberately ignoring NamSor's internal confidence scores in order to preserve the sample nature (i.e., representativeness of German researchers). Moving forward, we plan to incorporate NamSor's accuracy on first and second countries of origin, narrowing the sample to increase NamSor accuracy and assess the ratio accuracy/subsample to sample distance.

2. Systematic Literature Review and Mapping:

We are developing a systematic literature review (and accompanying scientific mapping) to identify all scholarly domains where NamSor has been applied. This review will examine both methodological and applied studies, focusing especially on cases where NamSor's classifications influenced empirical results and policy implications. By analyzing abstracts and outcomes through text analysis, we aim to quantify the extent of potential distortions or misinterpretations arising.

Open science practices

This study makes use of survey responses from the in-house DZHW WiBeF 2019 dataset and comparative results obtained through the NamSor commercial tool. Access to the WiBeF dataset was possible through institutional collaboration, but it is not publicly available due to confidentiality agreements and GDPR restrictions concerning personal data. Similarly, results generated through NamSor cannot be shared, as they would reveal the participants to the WiBeF surveys. While the underlying data and outputs cannot be openly released associated with names and surnames, detailed methodological descriptions are provided in the paper to ensure transparency and reproducibility of the analysis. No preregistration was undertaken.

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Author contributions

Matteo Ottaviani: Conceptualization, Data curation, Analysis, Writing – original draft, Writing – review and editing
Stephan Stahlschmidt: Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Writing—review and editing

Competing interests

The authors have no competing interests.

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